

Buddy Tutorial

This tutorial will teach you the basics of setting up pipelines on the Buddy platform.

You will be presented with this blank pipeline named “test-and-release”.

Click on **Add action** and add a new Action. You will be presented with these options

Configuration

Create a Node.js command action. This action runs **npm install** and **npm run build** to build this app.

The screenshot shows the configuration interface for a GitHub Actions workflow. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for Run, node@20, Services, Cache, Variables, Conditions, and Options. The main area is titled "COMMANDS" and contains a text editor with the following code:

```
# yarn install
npm install
npm run build
```

Below the code editor, there are two dropdown menus. The first is labeled "SHELL" and is set to "Bash". The second is labeled "ERROR HANDLING" and is set to "Mark as failed if any command throws an error". At the bottom of the configuration area, there is a large blue button labeled "Add this action".

The default container image is **node** with version **20** but let's change it to run in version **12**. You can type in the version select list and click on **12**.

Run node @ 12 Services Cache Variables Conditions Options

Image Packages & Tools

IMAGE LOCATION
Public registry Private registry From action

REGISTRY
Docker Hub Other

IMAGE
node (Official)

VERSION
12

USER
Optional. Overrides the default user to another user in the image.

OPTIONS
 Reset default image entrypoint
 Don't cache image between runs

12.22.12
12.22.11
12.22.10
12.22.9
12.22.8
12.22.7
12.22.6

Add this action

At last, change the action name to **build** in **Options** tab.

Run node @ 12 Services Cache Variables Conditions Options

ACTION NAME
build

Then add this action and this should be the result.

Pipelines / test-and-release main Run new

Runs Actions Filesystem Variables Analytics Settings YAML

On Run 1 On Failure On Cancel On Back to Green On Error Suppression On Wait for Human

build

Now create a Local shell command action bellow **build** action named **create file** that runs the command **echo 'File content' > new_file.txt**. It runs in a **ubuntu** image with version **20.04**.

The screenshot shows the configuration page for a 'Local shell' action. At the top, there are tabs for 'Run', 'ubuntu @ 20.04', 'Services', 'Cache', 'Variables', 'Conditions', and 'Options'. The main area is titled 'COMMANDS' and contains a text editor with the command `echo 'File content' > new_file.txt`. Below the editor are two dropdown menus: 'SHELL' set to 'Bash' and 'ERROR HANDLING' set to 'Mark as failed if any command throws an error'. A large blue button at the bottom says 'Add this action'.

Then add this action and this should be the result.

The screenshot shows the workflow configuration page. At the top, there are tabs for 'Runs', 'Actions', 'Filesystem', 'Variables', 'Analytics', 'Settings', and 'YAML'. Below the tabs are several event triggers: 'On Run 2', 'On Failure', 'On Cancel', 'On Back to Green', 'On Error Suppression', and 'On Wait for Human'. The workflow consists of two steps: 'build' and 'create file'. Both steps are shown with a green toggle switch and a three-dot menu icon.

You can also view this configuration in YAML format by clicking in **YAML** tab

Location: In-app Helpers Secrets automatically encrypted

YAML

```
- pipeline: "test-and-release"
  events:
    - type: "PUSH"
      refs:
        - "refs/heads/main"
      fail_on_prepare_env_warning: true
  actions:
    - action: "build"
      type: "BUILD"
      docker_image_name: "library/node"
      docker_image_tag: "12"
      execute_commands:
        - "# yarn install"
        - "npm install"
        - "npm run build"
      shell: "BASH"
    - action: "create file"
      type: "BUILD"
      docker_image_name: "library/ubuntu"
      docker_image_tag: "20.04"
```

To validate this configuration, click on **Run new** button.

Click **Run now** to run this configuration:

Pipelines / test-and-release / Run test-and-release

Options Variables at runtime Actions

RUN
Commit Branch Tag Pull request

COMMIT
TP Add Cypress tests
Missing something? [Fetch manually](#)
CCAEF2AED0...

REVISION ALREADY EXECUTED

DESCRIPTION
Optional. Markdown supported.

FLAGS
 Clear cache before running (Not recommended)

PRIORITY
Normal

SCHEDULE RUN
 Set date & time when run this pipeline

Run now

This configuration is validated when every action is green:

Pipelines / test-and-release / Runs / Run: #2 main

Run another...

Run Summary

- > Setup action 0s
- > build 15s
- > create file 3s

This is the end of the tutorial!